

A Constrained Decomposition Method for Myocardial Perfusion Quantification: Mitigating Partial Volume Effects

Yupeng Zhao¹ | Rie Beck Olin¹ | Esben Søvst Szocska Hansen³ | Christoffer Laustsen³ | Jan Henrik Ardenkjær-Larsen¹ | Lars G. Hanson^{1,2}

¹Department of Health Technology, Technical University of Denmark, Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark

²Danish Research Centre for Magnetic Resonance, Centre for Functional and Diagnostic Imaging and Research, Copenhagen University Hospital Hvidovre, Denmark

³MR Research Centre, Aarhus University, Aarhus, Denmark

Correspondence

Lars G. Hanson, Department of Health Technology, Danmarks Tekniske Universitet, Ørstedes Plads, Building 349, DK-2800 Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark. Email: lghan@dtu.dk

Funding Information

This work was supported by the European Unions Horizon 2020 research and innovation program; grant No 858149

Summary

We propose a constrained decomposition method to reduce partial volume effects in myocardial perfusion quantification. The method is capable of separating perfusion and arterial signal components.

Purpose: In myocardial perfusion MRI, the blood pool signal is much higher than the tissue signal. Due to partial volume effects, the tissue signal is contaminated by the neighbouring right/left ventricular blood pool signal, which results in perfusion overestimation. Although partial volume effects decrease with increasing spatial resolution, it remains inevitable due to the spatial adjacency of the ventricular blood pool and myocardium. Standard voxel-wise perfusion quantification cannot address this problem, and coarse spatial resolution is moreover often needed, for example to get sufficient temporal resolution and signal-to-noise ratio. A method is needed to separate the blood pool and tissue signals to reduce partial volume effects.

Methods: Myocardial perfusion data was decomposed into left/right ventricular blood pool and myocardium components based on prior knowledge of signal characteristics. This was mathematically formulated as matrix decomposition, involving the solving of two constrained least-squared problems. The method was validated through simulation and was compared with voxel-wise analysis in both simulated and in vivo myocardial perfusion datasets.

Results: The results from both simulation and in vivo experiments demonstrated the effectiveness of the constrained decomposition method in separating the myocardium from the ventricular blood pool components. Moreover, simulation results showed smaller estimation errors with the proposed method compared to the reference method. In vivo results showed that perfusion values estimated by the proposed method align more closely with literature values than those obtained through the reference method.

Conclusion: The proposed method effectively separated perfusion and arterial signal components, reducing partial volume effects.

KEYWORDS:

cardiac perfusion, MRI, partial volume, constrained decomposition

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1 | INTRODUCTION

Coronary artery disease (CAD) is a common cardiovascular disease characterized by the narrowing or obstruction of coronary arteries, and it stands as a prominent global cause of mortality. Approximately 17.9 million individuals worldwide die from CAD, accounting for a third of all global deaths (World Health Organization¹).

Cardiac MRI, a non-invasive technique free from ionizing radiation, offers a comprehensive assessment of cardiac anatomy and functions. Consequently, it has found extensive application in clinical CAD diagnosis^{2,3,4}. DCE-MRI utilizes a saturation recovery sequence to generate T_1 -weighted images dynamically capturing tissue signal changes following injection of a gadolinium-based contrast agent^{5,6,7}. It is regarded as the gold standard for myocardial perfusion measurement among MRI methods⁸. The recorded signal variation reflect changes of contrast agent concentration, and constitute the data analyzed to estimate the perfusion. A linear correlation between the MR signal and the contrast concentration is assumed throughout the manuscript, though this may sometimes be challenged, e.g., due to signal saturation for Gd-based agents. The linear assumption is common, also for other perfusion imaging techniques (e.g., positron emission tomography, PET), where a recorded signal is proportional to the contrast agent concentration. The potential need for a non-linear mapping is beyond the scope of the current manuscript.

Despite its widespread use, DCE-MRI presents challenges. Firstly, it offers an indirect measure of perfusion, leading to potential inaccuracies in absolute perfusion quantification⁹. Secondly, concerns exist regarding gadolinium retention in the body and its environmental impact^{10,11,12,13}. As an alternative to DCE-MRI, some studies have indicated the feasibility of measuring myocardial perfusion using hyperpolarized ^{13}C -based contrast agents^{14,15,16,17,18}. Unlike Gd-based measurements, where the contrast agent concentration is indirectly linked to the MR signal through changes in relaxation time, in the case of hyperpolarized ^{13}C , the contrast agent concentration is directly and linearly related to the measured MR signal. However, the different decay rates of hyperpolarized arterial and tissue signals may introduce inaccuracies in the estimation of perfusion values.

In myocardial perfusion MRI, images must be acquired repeatedly and sufficiently fast to avoid temporal undersampling. Repeated image acquisition is typically required for each heartbeat, and the heart rate constrains the spatial resolution and coverage. Therefore,

myocardial perfusion MRI typically has a low spatial resolution, especially for 3D coverage. As dictated by cardiac physiology, where only 5% of blood flows from left ventricle into the coronary artery, there is a large amplitude difference between the ventricular blood pool and myocardial signals, causing myocardial signal contamination and subsequent overestimation of perfusion due to the partial volume effect^{17,19}. In both Gd-based and hyperpolarized ^{13}C -based perfusion measurements, partial volume effects are present. Although the partial volume effects decrease with increasing spatial resolution, it is inevitable even in high-resolution perfusion images. This is due to the proximity of the ventricular blood pool to the myocardium.

Perfusion quantification is typically based on an assumption of linear responses, which have proven a widely useful approximation. Hence the local haemodynamics can be described by an impulse response function, often normalized by scaling with the perfusion estimate, and then referred to as the residue function in the context of perfusion imaging. Existing perfusion quantification methods fall into two categories, some with elements of both: model-dependent and model-independent methods^{20,21}. Model-dependent methods involve modeling of the residue function with a decay function (often exponential) and estimating perfusion through model fitting. In contrast, model-independent methods estimate the residue function via deconvolution between tissue signal and arterial signal. However, both methods are voxel-wise and do not address the partial volume issue. This study introduces a data-driven perfusion quantification method relying on constrained decomposition. Inspired by non-negative matrix factorization theory^{22,23}, the method is tailored to myocardial perfusion quantification, incorporating constraints to enforce prior knowledge of the residue function being positive and monotonically decreasing.

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Voxel-wise model independent perfusion quantification method

This work employs a widely used voxel-wise model-independent perfusion quantification method as a reference method²⁰. The residue function is estimated by deconvolution. According to the central volume theory, the tissue signal time course $C_t(t)$ is the convolution between the arterial input function (AIF) $C_a(t)$ and residue function $R(t)$ scaled by the perfusion F . In the reference method, the AIF is typically chosen from a

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voxel containing only arterial blood. For myocardial perfusion data, the AIF is usually selected as the mean signal from the left ventricular blood pool region. In contrast, the constrained decomposition method estimates the AIF through model fitting to ensure it represents the signals within the left ventricular blood pool region. The perfusion model is described as follows:

$$C_t(t) = F \int_0^t C_a(\tau) R(t - \tau) d\tau = F C_a(t) * R(t) \quad (1)$$

The equation is temporally discretized and rewritten in matrix form:

$$\mathbf{C} = F \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{b} \quad (2)$$

Matrix \mathbf{A} is a convolution matrix with time-shifted versions of C_a as columns, vector \mathbf{C} is a tissue signal time course, and \mathbf{b} is the residue function. To solve \mathbf{b} in Equation 2, an error minimization problem is formulated, incorporating the fact that the true residue function is a decreasing function, since contrast agents that has left the tissue cannot reappear unless it is recirculated. This property is added as a constraint in the minimization problem that is solved using the quadratic programming method²⁴ with \mathbf{G} being the differential operator expressed as a matrix.

$$\min_{\mathbf{b}} \|\mathbf{C} - F \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{b}\|, \text{ subject to: } \mathbf{G}\mathbf{b} < 0 \quad (3)$$

2.2 | Constrained decomposition method

2.2.1 | Mathematical modeling

In myocardial perfusion MRI, the signals from the ventricular blood pool and myocardium exhibit distinct temporal characteristics and amplitudes. Based on these differences in signal shape, the time series, denoted as $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, can be decomposed into right/left ventricular blood pool (RV/LV) and tissue (myocardium) components through a product of weightings $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times c}$, and time courses, $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{c \times n}$, where m is the number of voxels, c is the number of components and n is number of time points:

$$\mathbf{X} \approx \mathbf{W}\mathbf{H} \quad (4)$$

To estimate \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{H} , we iteratively solve two constrained least squares (LS) problems mathematically expressed as follows:

Given \mathbf{H} :

$$\min_{\mathbf{W}} \|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{W}\mathbf{H}\|_2, \text{ subject to: } \mathbf{W} > 0 \quad (5)$$

Given \mathbf{W} :

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\mathbf{H}} \|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{W}\mathbf{H}\|_2, \\ & \text{subject to: } \mathbf{G}\mathbf{R} < 0, \mathbf{H} > 0, \mathbf{R} > 0, \\ & \mathbf{R} = \text{deconv}(\mathbf{H}_{\text{AIF}}, \mathbf{H}_{\text{tissue}}) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Here, \mathbf{R} represents the vectorized residue function derived from the tissue signal $\mathbf{H}_{\text{tissue}}$, deconvolved with the arterial input function \mathbf{H}_{AIF} , and \mathbf{G} denotes the differential operator. The first LS problem entails solving for \mathbf{W} given \mathbf{H} with elements in \mathbf{W} constrained to positive values. The second LS problem involves solving for \mathbf{H} given \mathbf{W} . The residue function is known to be monotonically decreasing, and this constraint is enforced. Both the residue function and time courses are known to be non-negative, and these constraints are also enforced.

This general idea is applicable when the AIF is common to all tissue voxels. This can be a good approximation for cardiac perfusion imaging in a healthy heart, for example. The idea is further developed below with solutions to practical problems for the specific case of cardiac perfusion imaging, and the resulting method is demonstrated. Even when based on general principles, the practical implementations will likely need adaption, when the method is applied to other data, e.g., other initialization values for other organs. This is outside the scope of the current manuscript focused on proof-of-concept exemplified for specific data in need of a method addressing partial volume problems.

2.2.2 | Practical Implementation

The algorithm is implemented in MATLAB (MathWorks) and the sequential quadratic programming (SQP) method is used to solve the non-linear constrained optimization problem²⁵. To enforce the imposed constraints on the solution, the constraints in the form of $c(x)$ are multiplied by a parameter denoted as λ before calling the optimization function. The value of λ is set sufficiently high (10^{200}) to effectively enforce the constraints (verified behaviour for any such high value). The pseudocode is outlined in Algorithms 1 and 2.

Data normalization

The MR data exhibits an arbitrary range. To standardize the value range and remove the baseline of the input signal time course, the input signal is normalized in two steps. Firstly, the mean of the noise is subtracted from the input signal time courses, denoted as \bar{S}_{noise} . Then, it is globally scaled by the maximum signal amplitude across the input data. Assuming white noise along the

signal time dimension, the noise level for each input signal time course is calculated as the mean over the time dimension of the signal time courses containing only noise. Mathematically, the data normalization process is described as follows:

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{normal}} = \frac{\mathbf{X}_{\text{input}} - \bar{S}_{\text{noise}}}{\max(\mathbf{X}_{\text{input}} - \bar{S}_{\text{noise}})} \quad (7)$$

This is a pragmatic choice to provide near zero mean noise and equal voxel weighting, desirable for the decomposition.

Stopping criteria

When estimating matrices \mathbf{W} or \mathbf{H} , the optimization of one of the matrices stops if the step size is smaller than 10^{-6} , calculated as the norm of $x_i - x_{i-1}$, where x_i and x_{i-1} are the estimates in the current and last step, or the maximum step number, set to 1000, is reached. After estimating the matrix \mathbf{W} , matrix \mathbf{H} is estimated. We define one iteration as finished when both matrices are updated once. The fitting error, defined as the norm of $\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{WH}$, was found to be a rapidly decaying function followed by a plateau. The fitting process was chosen to stop when the error reduction from the current iteration is smaller than 10% of the previous reduction or the maximum iteration number (3) has been reached, as indicated in Algorithm 1 and 2. We found that the optimization is robust to these choices and that they will primarily affect computation time rather than the obtained result.

Initialization

Matrix \mathbf{H} contains component time courses and the expected number of substantially different components needs to be chosen. For cardiac perfusion data, three components have been selected with the assumption that, within each compartment, the signal time courses are similar, except for variations in scaling: left/right ventricular blood pool(LV/RV) and myocardial tissue compartments. LV/RV time courses are initialized as the mean time course inside the LV/RV regions. The tissue signal time course is initialized based on the central volume theorem:

$$\mathbf{H}_{\text{tissue}} = \mathbf{H}_{\text{AIF}} * F e^{-\frac{t}{\text{MTT}}} \quad (8)$$

$\mathbf{H}_{\text{tissue}}$ and \mathbf{H}_{AIF} are tissue and LV signal time courses. The residue function is modeled as an exponential decay function with perfusion (F) as amplitude and mean transit time (MTT) as the time constant. Matrix \mathbf{W} is initialized as the product of the inverse of matrix \mathbf{H} and the data matrix \mathbf{X} .

Multi-start approach

Due to the potential non-convex nature of this optimization problem, the result of a single optimization may

depend on the initialization. To reduce the unavoidable risk of ending in a local minimum, the optimization is repeated with ten different initial values of F and MTT (100 repetitions in total). The initial value ranges are chosen to cover the potential F and MTT values for pigs and human (F :0.6-6 mL g⁻¹ min⁻¹ and MTT: 1-20 s)^{26 27 28}. The initial values are uniformly sampled from this range. To select the best solution, a tissue mask is created based on anatomical images. The best-estimated perfusion map is selected as the one with the lowest fitting errors inside the tissue mask, see Algorithm 1.

2.3 | Validation

Dynamic myocardial perfusion images are simulated for validation, including LV/RV and myocardium components. The chosen component weight maps and time courses are illustrated in Figure 1. To simulate partial volume effects, the weight maps are smoothed by gaussian blurring. The MR signal is calculated by multiplying the weights with component curves before noise is added. Monte Carlo simulation is performed with both the proposed and reference methods. Four different myocardium SNR levels with Gaussian noise are simulated, and for each, the estimation is repeated ten times with different noise realizations. The mean and standard deviation are calculated for each SNR level and method.

2.4 | Error simulation

The myocardial tissue signal curve may be delayed compared to the AIF in myocardial perfusion data. This delay time is around 1.4 ± 1.4 s for pigs at rest²⁹. Due to the delay, the onset of the residue function is shifted, potentially compromising the imposed constraints. A simulation is performed to investigate the errors caused by delay. The data used in this simulation is shown in Figure 1. The simulated delay time ranges from 0 to 3 s.

2.5 | In vivo study

2.5.1 | HP001 pig cardiac data

Animal handling

Three healthy 40 kg female Danish domestic pigs participated and were handled as described in³⁰. All animals were treated according to the Danish regulation of animal experiments (J.nr.: 2014-15-2934-01013). Cardiac stress was pharmacologically induced by continuous intravenous infusion (600 mL h⁻¹) of adenosine

FIGURE 1 Dynamic MRI perfusion series simulation. The simulation includes RV/LV and myocardial components. The component weight maps are created to resemble anatomical structure and blurred by a Gaussian filter to create partial volume effects. The ventricular blood pool component time courses are simulated using the gamma variate function. The tissue time course is simulated as the convolution between left ventricular blood pool and residue function scaled by the perfusion. The dynamic images are simulated by multiplying component weight maps with their time courses.

(5 mg mL⁻¹) and dobutamine (12.5 mg mL⁻¹) in saline. Imaging started 5 minutes into the stress infusion.

Hyperpolarization

HP001(bis-1,1-(hydroxymethyl)-[1-¹³C]cyclopropane-d8)(GE Healthcare, UK) was hyperpolarized using the dissolution dynamic nuclear polarization method (dDNP). 300 μ L HP001 with 40 mmol L⁻¹ trityl radical(AH111501, GE Healthcare, UK) was polarized with a SpinAligner (Polarize, Denmark), and dissolved into 15 mL saline providing 166 mmol L⁻¹ HP001 solution.

MR data acquisition

Stress myocardial HP001 (¹³C) images were acquired from three pigs with a 3D gradient echo stack-of-spirals sequence in the short axis view with diastolic gating. Imaging parameters: FOV=150×150×100 mm³, resolution=3×3×10 mm³, TR/TE=44/1 ms, flip angle=10°, image frame time=half cardiac cycle, number of frames=60.

2.5.2 | DCE perfusion data

DOTAREM(Guerbet, France) was employed as MR contrast agent for a DCE scan, and the injection volume was determined based on the recommended dose, which is 0.2 mL kg⁻¹. Stress ¹H

saturation-recovery DCE-MRI data were acquired for the same three pigs. The acquisition parameters: FOV=350×350 mm², resolution=1.35×1.35 mm², saturation recovery time/TE/TR=118/1.12/2.3 ms, flip angle=20°, slice thickness=8 mm, slice spacing=20 mm, number of slices=3, image frame time=1 cardiac cycle, number of frames=64. The MR signal was converted to contrast agents concentration in tissue as described in³¹.

2.5.3 | Pyruvate human cardiac data

[1-¹³C] Pyruvate was polarized using a SPINlab DNP polarizer (GE Healthcare). The sample preparation and hyperpolarization process is described in³². Hyperpolarized imaging was obtained using cardiac-gated spectral-spatial (SPSP) excitation with spiral read-out acquisition. Patient data were obtained with these parameters: TE=10 ms, read-out period=27 ms, flip angle=5°, FOV=340×340 mm, matrix=90×90, in-plane resolution=8×8 mm in one short axis slice with 30 mm slice thickness. Image frame time is 1 cardiac cycle.

Figure 2 shows dynamic myocardial perfusion images. For each dataset introduced above, a single slice from the middle of the heart is displayed. Before processing the perfusion data, a region of interest (ROI) mask was manually drawn based on overlaying perfusion and anatomical images. This mask contains left ventricle and

Hyperpolarized HP001

Gd

Hyperpolarized pyruvate human

Frame →

FIGURE 2 Dynamic perfusion images of the heart using Hyperpolarized HP001 as a contrast agent (top), DCE-MRI (middle), and Hyperpolarized pyruvate as a contrast agent (bottom). The hyperpolarized HP001 and DCE-MRI data were acquired from a pig model, while hyperpolarized pyruvate data were obtained from a human. The contrast agent initially enters the right ventricle, followed by flush out, and subsequently enters the left ventricle before being flushed out.

a portion of right ventricle proximate to the left ventricle for the following reasons: Firstly, the left ventricular wall is thicker than the right ventricular wall. Typically, the left ventricular wall exhibits a much stronger perfusion signal than the right ventricular wall, posing challenges in accurately quantifying perfusion values for the right ventricular wall. Therefore, our focus is primarily on quantifying perfusion values in the left ventricular wall. Secondly, considering the potential inhomogeneity of blood flow within the right ventricular region, the partial inclusion of the right ventricular region near the left ventricle can provide a better separation of myocardium components from the RV component. Additionally, this selective inclusion of the right ventricular region reduces input data size, contributing to a shorter computation time.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Validation

Figure 3 depicts the Monte Carlo simulation results for the proposed and reference methods. Observing the standard deviation and error map, it is evident that the proposed method exhibits significantly lower estimation errors and standard deviation in comparison to the

reference method. The estimated perfusion map illustrates the ability of the proposed method to separate the myocardium from the RV/LV components. In contrast, the reference method tends to overestimate the perfusion, particularly in the tissue region close to the LV component.

3.2 | Error simulation

Figure 4 shows the quantitative error induced by the delay between the AIF and tissue curve. The error map indicates that the delay leads to an underestimation of perfusion. As the delay time increases, the estimation error also increases.

3.3 | In vivo study

The proposed method was tested on three in vivo datasets. Figure 5 shows the in vivo results, including estimated time courses, weight maps of AIF, tissue and RV components, residue functions, and perfusion maps. Various insights can be obtained from Figure 5. Firstly, different components are spatially separated. By visually inspecting the estimated weight map and component time course, the right ventricular blood pool component

Simulated perfusion estimation by the **reference method** and the **constrained decomposition method**

FIGURE 3 Monte Carlo simulation results. The blue font indicates the proposed method and red font indicates the reference method. The figure shows the estimated perfusion map, standard deviation and absolute error for four different myocardium SNR levels (SNR=25,50,100,150). The scaling is the same for each pair of images that should be compared. The unit in all plots is mL/g/min.

is correctly estimated using the current approach, which includes a portion of the right ventricular region near the left ventricle inside the ROI. The estimated residue functions are monotonically decreasing, which reflects the imposed constraints. The estimated perfusion values in Gd and hyperpolarized HP001 datasets are in the range of the literature values^{26,27}, while the estimated perfusion values in the hyperpolarized pyruvate data are lower than the normal perfusion values for human, which are around $1.5 \text{ mL g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. Compared to perfusion maps obtained from Gd measurements, those obtained from hyperpolarized measurements show lower image quality.

Comparing the proposed method with the reference method in Figure 6, it is evident that the reference method tends to highly overestimate perfusion values, particularly in hyperpolarized datasets. Partial volume effects are less pronounced in the DCE dataset due to its higher spatial resolution. In this dataset, the reference method overestimates perfusion values in the myocardial region close to the ventricular blood pool, while perfusion values slightly further from the ventricular blood

pool still align with the reported range in the literature (around 1.5 and $4 \text{ mL g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ for rest/stress perfusion values)^{26,27}.

Ideally, in a region without partial volume effects, the perfusion values estimated by the proposed method should align with those estimated by the reference method. To investigate this, a correlation study was conducted as follows: Using the Gd perfusion map estimated by the reference method, a region less affected by the partial volume effect was identified by applying a threshold set at the literature value in stress condition of $4 \text{ mL g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. Subsequently, the perfusion values estimated by both methods within the masked region were correlated. Figure 7 illustrates a strong correlation ($R = 0.89$) in perfusion values estimated by reference and proposed methods within regions less affected by partial volume. However, the reference method demonstrates overestimation compared to the proposed method ($y = 0.6x$), due to the small degree of partial volume effect still present in the analyzed region. This observation is

FIGURE 4 Quantified perfusion estimation error caused by the delay between AIF and tissue signal time curve. The unit of all plots is mL/g/min.

further confirmed in Figure 5, where DCE-MRI perfusion values estimated by the reference method (green color) are higher than those estimated by the proposed method (blue color) within regions less affected by partial volume.

4 | DISCUSSION

This study addresses perfusion overestimation due to partial volume effects by introducing a data-driven

method to separate myocardial signal from ventricular blood pool signals, thus mitigating the impact of partial volume effects on perfusion estimation. The method is validated using simulations and is compared against a voxel-wise perfusion estimation method, serving as the reference method. Furthermore, the study quantifies the estimation error resulting from the time delay between the AIF and the tissue curve, based on a simulated dataset. Finally, the method is tested on in vivo datasets and compared with the reference method.

FIGURE 5 Estimated component time courses, maps and residue functions estimated from three in vivo datasets: a) hyperpolarized HP001 measured in a pig, b) hyperpolarized pyruvate in a human, and c) Gd DCE data from a pig. Three components are included in the analysis: right/left ventricular blood pool and a myocardium component. The estimated component maps show that all three components are spatially separated in all three datasets. The estimated residue functions in all three data sets are decreasing functions reflecting the imposed constraints.

FIGURE 6 Perfusion maps from three in vivo datasets estimated by the proposed constrained decomposition method and the reference method. The myocardium region in the perfusion maps is masked.

4.1 | Simulation

Simulated MRI perfusion data serves as the ground truth for method validation. The simulation results, depicted

FIGURE 7 Correlation of perfusion values estimated by the proposed and reference methods inside regions less affected by partial volume effects. A strong correlation ($R=0.89$) is demonstrated between the two methods. The reference method shows overestimation compared to the proposed method ($y = 0.6x$)

in Figure 3, confirm that the proposed method effectively separates the myocardium component from the left/right ventricular blood pool components, providing accurate perfusion estimation. In contrast, the voxel-wise perfusion quantification method overestimates perfusion values, especially in tissue regions where partial volume effects are prominent.

Analysis of the error simulation indicates that a transit delay causes underestimation of the perfusion values, and that the error increases with increasing delay time. For a delay within the range 0-3 s, the maximal error is $-0.4 \text{ mL g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. This error is relatively small compared to the average rest perfusion value in humans, around $1.5\text{-}3 \text{ mL g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. However, when using the method, this potential underestimation has to be considered.

Another important consideration is the uniqueness of the solution to the optimization problem $\min_{\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{H}} \|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{W}\mathbf{H}\|_2$. If \mathbf{H}_{est} and \mathbf{W}_{est} constitutes a solution to the optimization problem, we can obtain infinitely many solutions with the same fitting errors by scaling \mathbf{H}_{est} by any positive real number α and \mathbf{W}_{est} by the inverse of α . Thus, there is an infinite number of solutions to the optimization problem, differing by a simple scaling. Perfusion F is calculated through the deconvolution between the arterial input function (AIF) and tissue time course, $\alpha\mathbf{H}_{\text{est}}$ and $\frac{1}{\alpha}\mathbf{W}_{\text{est}}$, described mathematically as $F\mathbf{R} = \text{deconv}\left(\frac{1}{\alpha}w_{\text{AIF}} \alpha\mathbf{H}_{\text{AIF}}, \frac{1}{\alpha}w_{\text{tissue}}\alpha\mathbf{H}_{\text{tissue}}\right)$,

which shows that perfusion estimates are independent of the scaling factor. However, this example only illustrates that all solutions differing by scaling yield the same perfusion estimates, but potentially other solutions could exist. The constraints imposed on the optimization problem help narrow down the set of solutions, which may be unique except for scaling. This is supported by the multi-start approach that resulted in unique perfusion estimates in both simulation and for in vivo data.

Three in vivo datasets are introduced, covering both conventional DCE-MRI and the newly developed hyperpolarized ^{13}C perfusion techniques. The selected subjects encompass both animals and humans. The conclusions drawn from the simulation are reaffirmed in the in vivo datasets. In all three datasets, the components are well separated, and the estimated residue function adheres to the imposed constraints. Furthermore, the estimated perfusion values fall within the range reported in the literature^{26 27}, except for the hyperpolarized pyruvate data. The estimated perfusion values are lower, potentially due to the influence of metabolic processes on the pyruvate signal. In contrast, the reference method significantly overestimates the perfusion values in the myocardium region proximal to the right/left ventricular blood pool. Compared to perfusion maps obtained from Gd measurements, those derived from hyperpolarized measurements exhibit lower image quality. This

Algorithm 1 Pseudocode

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01 masks: = left/right ventricular blood pool and tissue
02 masks;
03 X: =  $n \times m$  matrix of normalized image data;
04 for perf: 10 initial perfusion values; do
05   for mtt: 10 initial mean transit time values; do
06     H: = 3 column-matrix of time courses;
07     H(:,1):=mean left ventricular blood pool time
08     course;
09     H(:,2):=tissue signal time course  $\mathbf{H}_{lv} *
10     \text{perf } e^{-\frac{t}{mtt}}$ ; (* denote convolution operation)
11     H(:,3):=mean right ventricular blood pool time
12     course;
13     W: = product of the inverse of matrix H and
14     the data matrix X;
15     West, Hest, errormap: = W, H components and
16     error maps estimated by the decomposition function;
17     errormean: = the mean of values in errormap
18     inside tissue mask;
19   end for
20 end for
21 Hfinal and Wfinal: = Hest and West with smallest
22 errormean;
23 perfusion map: = the first element of deconvolution
24 between LV and tissue signal time course.

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Algorithm 2 Decomposition function definition

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29 Input: H0, W0: = initialized H and W matrix;
30 Hest = H0;
31 while error reduction is larger than 10% of the pre-
32 vious reduction AND iteration number < maximum
33 iteration number; do
34   West: = solve Equation 5 using MATLAB fmincon
35   function;
36   Hest: = solve Equation 6 using MATLAB fmincon
37   function;
38 end while
39 errormap: =  $\|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{W}_{est} \mathbf{H}_{est}\|_2$ ;
40 Output: West, Hest, errormap

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is due to the lower myocardial SNR in hyperpolarized myocardial data compared to Gd-enhanced data, which can be seen from the dynamic images of all three datasets in Figure 2. The correlation results show strongly correlated perfusion values between proposed and reference methods inside a region less affected by partial volume effects. This positive finding indicate that the in vivo perfusion values estimated by the proposed method are trustworthy. The current study demonstrates the application of the method in cardiac perfusion data. However,

it is important to note that the method is not confined to cardiac perfusion applications. It can be extended to other organs for which tissues share a common AIF and exhibit similar signal time courses except for scaling, e.g., kidney. When extending the application of the method to different organs, consideration should be given to adapting the component choices and initialization.

4.2 | Limitations

The presented work has some limitations.

Firstly, the method is based on the assumption that all voxels in the ROI share the same residue function except for the scaling. This approximation is valid in the case of, for example, the healthy heart and kidney³³. However, it breaks down in the case of brain with collateral blood supply, and heart ischemia, where part of the heart tissue may have a delayed blood supply.

Secondly, the method employs Sequential Quadratic Programming (SQP) as the optimization method. This operates on full matrices and utilizes dense linear algebra. Consequently, it demands significant memory access for matrix storage and a prolonged execution time. The computational complexity is further increased by the multi-start approach involving 100 initializations. To address this, the multi-start approach is implemented as parallel computing to reduce computation time. To approach the global minimum, it is ideal to densely sample initial parameter values within their respective intervals. However, the trade-off between the number of initial points and computational time needs careful consideration. The choice of 100 initial points is made to cover potential parameter value ranges while maintaining a reasonable computation time. The application of the method to 3D datasets faces constraints imposed by limitations in computer hardware and computation time. Ideally, when dealing with 3D data, the entire volumetric dataset should be processed as a single unit using the proposed method. However, due to limitations in computational power and extended processing times, the current practice involves dividing 3D myocardial perfusion data into individual single slices, each processed separately. For different slices, the AIF are estimated differently. This approach is suboptimal and may lead to inconsistencies in the estimated perfusion values across slices. However, strategies for handling large 3D dataset has been proposed in²³. These strategies can be directly adopted.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

The developed data-driven perfusion quantification method effectively separated tissue components from arterial components and reduces partial volume effects in perfusion estimates. The proposed method demonstrated superior accuracy in perfusion estimation compared to standard voxel-wise perfusion quantification method. The method is only applicable when the residue function varies insignificantly between tissues, which limits the range of acceptable tissue heterogeneity.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work has been funded by the European Unions Horizon 2020 research and innovation program; grant No 858149

REFERENCES

1. WHO . Available from: *Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) (WHO)*. 2021.
2. Rajiah Prabhakar, Desai Milind Y., Kwon Deborah, Flamm Scott D.. MR Imaging of Myocardial Infarction. *RadioGraphics*. 2013;33(5):1383–1412.
3. Roos A, Wall E E, Brusckhe A V, Voorthuisen A E. Magnetic resonance imaging in the diagnosis and evaluation of myocardial infarction. *Magnetic resonance quarterly*. 1991;7(3):191–207.
4. Buffa Vitaliano, Di Renzi Paolo. CMR in the diagnosis of ischemic heart disease. *La radiologia medica*. 2020;125(11):1114–1123.
5. Franks Russell, Plein Sven, Chiribiri Amedeo. Clinical Application of Dynamic Contrast Enhanced Perfusion Imaging by Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance. *Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine*. 2021;8:768563.
6. Yankeelov Thomas E., Gore John C. Dynamic Contrast Enhanced Magnetic Resonance Imaging in Oncology: Theory, Data Acquisition, Analysis, and Examples. *Current Medical Imaging Reviews*. 2007;3(2):91–107.
7. Gordon Yaron, Partovi Sasan, Müller-Eschner Matthias, et al. Dynamic contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging: fundamentals and application to the evaluation of the peripheral perfusion. *Cardiovascular Diagnosis and Therapy*. 2014;4(2):147.
8. Hamirani Yasmin S., Kramer Christopher M.. Cardiac MRI assessment of myocardial perfusion. *Future cardiology*. 2014;10(3):349.
9. Schwitter Juerg. Myocardial perfusion imaging by cardiac magnetic resonance. *Journal of Nuclear Cardiology*. 2006;13(6):841–854.
10. Ramalho Miguel, Ramalho Joana, Burke Lauren M., Semelka Richard C.. Gadolinium Retention and Toxicity An Update. *Advances in Chronic Kidney Disease*. 2017;24(3):138–146.
11. Tedeschi Enrico, Caranci Ferdinando, Giordano Flavio, Angelini Valentina, Coccozza Sirio, Brunetti Arturo. Gadolinium retention in the body: what we know and what we can do. *La radiologia medica*. 2017;122(8):589–600.
12. Rogowska Justyna, Olkowska Ewa, Ratajczyk Wojciech, Wolska Lidia. Gadolinium as a new emerging contaminant of aquatic environments. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*. 2018;37(6):1523–1534.
13. Kümmerer Klaus, Helmert Eckard. Hospital Effluents as a Source of Gadolinium in the Aquatic Environment. *Environmental Science & Technology*. 2000;34(4):573–577.
14. Zhao Yupeng, Olin Rie Beck, Hanson Lars G., Hansen Esben Søvsø Szocska, Laustsen Christoffer, Ardenkjær-Larsen Jan Henrik. 3D myocardial perfusion quantification using hyperpolarized HP001. In: ISMRM & ISMRT Annual Meeting & Exhibition; 2023; Toronto.
15. Lewis Andrew J. M., Tyler Damian J., Rider Oliver. Clinical Cardiovascular Applications of Hyperpolarized Magnetic Resonance. *Cardiovascular Drugs and Therapy*. 2020;34(2):231.
16. Fuetterer Maximilian, Busch Julia, Traechtler Julia, et al. Quantitative myocardial first-pass cardiovascular magnetic resonance perfusion imaging using hyperpolarized [1-13C] pyruvate. *Journal of Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance*. 2018;20(1):73.
17. Fuetterer Maximilian, Busch Julia, Peereboom Sophie M., et al. Hyperpolarized 13C urea myocardial first-pass perfusion imaging using velocity-selective excitation. *Journal of Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance*. 2017;19:46.
18. Tyler Damian J. Cardiovascular Applications of Hyperpolarized MRI. *Current Cardiovascular Imaging Reports*. 2011;4(2):108–115.
19. Köstler Herbert, Ritter Christian, Reiss-Zimmermann Martin, Beer Meinrad, Hahn Dietbert, Sandstede Jörn. Correction for partial volume errors in MR heart perfusion imaging. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2004;51(4):848–852.
20. Østergaard Leif, Weisskoff Robert M., Chesler David A., Gyldensted Carsten, Rosen Bruce R.. High resolution measurement of cerebral blood flow using intravascular tracer bolus passages. Part I: Mathematical approach and statistical analysis. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 1996;36(5):715–725.
21. Østergaard Leif, Sorensen Alma Gregory, Kwong Kenneth K., Weisskoff Robert M., Gyldensted Carsten, Rosen Bruce R.. High resolution measurement of cerebral blood flow using intravascular tracer bolus passages. Part II: Experimental comparison and preliminary results. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 1996;36(5):726–736.
22. Berry Michael W., Browne Murray, Langville Amy N., Pauca V. Paul, Plemmons Robert J.. Algorithms and applications for approximate nonnegative matrix factorization. *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis*. 2007;52(1):155–173.

- 01 23. Rahbek Sofie, Madsen Kristoffer H., Lundell Henrik,
02 Mahmood Faisal, Hanson Lars G.. Data-driven separation
03 of MRI signal components for tissue characterization.
04 *Journal of Magnetic Resonance*. 2021;333:107103. 54
55
05 24. Coleman Thomas F., Li Yuying. A Reflective Newton
06 Method for Minimizing a Quadratic Function Subject
07 to Bounds on Some of the Variables. *SIAM Journal on*
08 *Optimization*. 1996;6(4):1040–1058. 56
57
09 25. Powell M. J. D.. Variable metric methods for con-
10 strained optimization. In: Bachem Achim, Korte Bern-
11 hard, Grötschel Martin, eds. *Mathematical programming*
12 *the state of the art: Bonn 1982*, Berlin, Heidelberg:
13 Springer Berlin Heidelberg 1983 (pp. 288–311). 58
59
14 26. Kajander Sami A., Joutsiniemi Esa, Saraste Markku,
15 et al. Clinical Value of Absolute Quantification of
16 Myocardial Perfusion With ^{15}O -Water in Coronary
17 Artery Disease. *Circulation: Cardiovascular Imaging*.
18 2011;4(6):678–684. 60
61
19 27. Husso Minna, Nissi Mikko J., Kuivanen Antti, et al.
20 Quantification of porcine myocardial perfusion with mod-
21 ified dual bolus MRI a prospective study with a PET
22 reference. *BMC Medical Imaging*. 2019;19(1):1–11. 62
63
23 28. Heinonen Ilkka, Kudomi Nobuyuki, Kempainen Jukka,
24 et al. Myocardial blood flow and its transit time,
25 oxygen utilization, and efficiency of highly endurance-
26 trained human heart. *Basic Research in Cardiology*.
27 2014;109(4):1–13. 64
65
28 29. Jerosch-Herold M., Hu Xudong, Murthy N.S., Seetham-
29 rajur R.T.. Time delay for arrival of MR contrast agent
30 in collateral-dependent myocardium. *IEEE Transactions*
31 *on Medical Imaging*. 2004;23(7):881–890. 66
67
32 30. Laustsen Christoffer, Hansen Esben Søvsø Szocska, Kjær-
33 gaard Uffe, Bertelsen Lotte Bonde, Ringgaard Steffen,
34 StødkildeJørgensen Hans. Acute porcine renal metabolic
35 effect of endogastric soft drink administration assessed
36 with hyperpolarized ^{113}C pyruvate. *Magnetic Resonance*
37 *in Medicine*. 2015;74(2):558. 68
69
38 31. Zöllner Frank G., Weisser Gerald, Reich Marcel, et al.
39 UMMPerfusion: an Open Source Software Tool Towards
40 Quantitative MRI Perfusion Analysis in Clinical Routine.
41 *Journal of Digital Imaging*. 2013;26(2):344–352. 70
71
42 32. Uthayakumar Biranavan, Soliman Hany, Bragagnolo
43 Nadia D., et al. Age-associated change in pyru-
44 vate metabolism investigated with hyperpolarized ^{13}C -
45 MRI of the human brain. *Human Brain Mapping*.
46 2023;44(10):4052–4063. 72
73
47 33. Nieman Koen, Balla Sujana. Dynamic CT Myocardial
48 Perfusion Imaging. *Journal of cardiovascular computed*
49 *tomography*. 2020;14(4):303. 74
75
50 76
51 77
52 78
53 79
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